

Traveler's portable plate absorber for field applications

Robert Mores

University of Applied Sciences Hamburg, Hamburg
robert.mores@haw-hamburg.de

Abstract

Fieldworkers in musical acoustics often conduct recordings of ethnological sound sources. Cataloguing musical instruments by means of impulse responses, for instance, demands independence from individual acoustical rooms in the field. A free field would be perfect, however, not while travelling. To achieve at least some neutrality, a simple plate absorber is suggested to suppress floor reflections. Wall or ceiling reflections might be late anyway when rooms are large, so reflection-free impulse responses can then be captured. Conventional molton curtains, otherwise not very absorbing, can be arranged to function as plate resonator. After some analytical suggestion and some impedance tube pretests, the absorption of an applicable absorber reaches down to 100 Hz as confirmed by ISO 365 measurements. Stripes of corrugated paper - arranged meander-like, upright on the floor - are strong enough to support some layers of molton curtain. The total weight is less than 1 kg and the volume is roughly 10 l for every m² of absorber, fitting into every travelling bag. But the absorber can also be build ad-hoc anywhere due to the simplicity of material and construction.

Introduction

Field recording of musical instruments ask for defined acoustical properties of the envelopping room, especially for purposes such as cataloguing or vibroacoustical analyses. A free field is usually not around in remote places, and it is impractical to move instruments, or to bring instruments and laboratory conditions together otherwise. A free field outside buildings is an option but regularly ambient sound sources are too loud. While it seems also impractical to carry loads of equipment, we search for a pragmatic way to build necessary absorbers ad-hoc, or carry such absorbers in a traveller's bag. Molton curtain, or at least cloth or dust sheets can be expected to be available in remote places, as well as corrugated paper, or at least cardboard.

Analytical suggestion

Molton curtain, while lying directly on the floor, or hanging directly at a wall has only little damping effect, and only for high frequencies. However, when arranged at a specific distance to a reflecting floor, or wall, the cloth acts as plate resonator. The resonator's frequency is determined by the distance and the mass per area according to

$$f = \frac{c}{2\pi} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{\rho}{m_A \cdot d}} \quad (1)$$

with the density, ρ , and the speed of sound, c , for the given air, the mass per area m_A , and distance d between cloth and reflecting plane. Using 1.2 kg/m³ (sea level at 20 °C), and one or two layers of conventional Molton curtain with $m_A = 300$ g/m², the frequency varies by distance as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Resonance frequency (analytical prediction) for one (o), two (\diamond), three (*), and four (\square) layers of cloth with 300g/m^2 arranged at distance d from a reflecting plane.

Impedance tube measurements

Fig. 2 shows the results of impedance tube measurements. One or two layers of mentioned Molton curtain show little absorption, when directly arranged at the reflecting surface, $d = 0$. When brought to distance relative to a reflector in the tube, the absorption increases, especially for low frequencies.

Fig. 2: Absorption measured in an impedance tube for one (-) and two (-) layers of cloth with 300g/m^2 arranged at distance $d = 0$ m from a reflective plane, as well as two layers arranged at distance d as indicated in the legend. Position of symbols indicate the predicted resonance frequency of the related plate absorber.

Predicted resonance frequencies are indicated in the figure where the respective legend symbol is placed on individual traces. The prediction is perfect for $d = 0.2$ m. For other frequencies it is moderate due to edge effects of the probe in the tube. Another impairing effect is the step at 125 Hz caused in the given impedance tube under all probe conditions. However, the general agreement of tube measurement results with prediction is encouraging, in particular the considerably high absorption at considerably low frequencies, below 200 Hz. These findings suggest to forward to the next step of application.

Absorption measurements in the hall room according to ISO 354

While heading towards applications two things change: (i) the sound is likely to be diffuse in real applications while it was directional in the impedance tube, (ii) the layers of cloth must be brought to a defined distance relative to a reflecting plane, by any means, which will introduce additional material. For reasons of a pragmatic approach, stripes of corrugated paper are used for keeping the space between plates. These are just strong enough to support some layers of cloth. The stripes are arranged meander-like on the floor before the layers of cloth are gently let down on the construction. Four layers of somewhat a thinner Molton curtain (160 g/m²) are used which amount to the same weight per area as above. The absorption quality is verified by measurements in a hall room. ISO 354 [1] is followed apart from a few parameters: the absorption area is not 10 m² to 12 m² but only some 4 m², and six rather than twelve speaker-microphone transfer-paths are used for averaging.

Fig. 3 shows the results for T30 measured in a hall room of volume $V = 152.2 \text{ m}^3$, at temperature $T = 27 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and at 30% relative humidity.

Fig. 3: RT30 measured according to ISO 354 in a hall room of volume $V = 152.2 \text{ m}^3$, without, and with an absorber of size 4 m², consisting of 10 cm high corrugated paper arranged on the floor, and four layers of Molton curtain, $m_A = 160 \text{ g/m}^2$ (nominal), on top.

The absorption coefficient, as derived from the RT30 times, respects given absorber edge effects [2], as measured during setup. Fig. 4 shows the results for absorption coefficients derived from T30 but also those derived from T20, in comparison with the prediction from the impedance tube.

Fig. 4: Absorption coefficient derived from ISO 354 measurements for the absorber of size 4 m², consisting of 10 cm high corrugated paper arranged on the floor, and four layers of Molton curtain, $m_A = 160 \text{ g/m}^2$ (nominal), on top.

In the application, the real absorber does fairly well reach into the low frequency range as predicted. An absorption of 0.5 was expected at about 180 Hz. The real absorber reaches this value at about 190 Hz (with reference to RT20), or 230 Hz (with reference to RT30). The other positive outcome is that the drop back at 1.25 kHz does not appear. The absorption rather continues to grow up to 100% due to the diffusive sound field.

Fig. 5 shows the implementation of a 17 cm high absorber, for which all measurements have been repeated. The higher absorber reaches further down in terms of frequency. An absorption coefficient of 0.5 was expected at 125 Hz and also confirmed at 125 Hz for the real absorber by both references, RT20 and RT30. An absorption of 0.8 is reached at 250 Hz. Unlike the 10 cm high absorber, the 17 cm high absorber shows a drop down to 0.75 at 1.25 kHz, predicted were 0.2 at 1.05 kHz, see Fig. 2. The higher the absorber, the more likely it seems that the predicted drop appears in the real absorber. However, the drop is much weaker than expected.

Fig. 5: Floor absorber consisting of (left) a supporting structure made of corrugated paper with (center) four layers of Molton, $m_A = 160 \text{ g/m}^2$, on top, (right) side view of the 17 cm high absorber.

To conclude, the results from the impedance tube can be used as a predictor for the real absorber in a diffuse sound field. The real absorber is likely to maintain a high absorption, without a strong drop, throughout the frequency range, beginning with a lower bound frequency somewhat higher than predicted.

Application

An absorber can now be realized at low weight. For instance, a 1 m^2 absorber arranged on the floor should be sufficient to record guitar impulse responses. The total mass is about 600 g for the Molton and 200 g for the corrugated paper. The volume is less than 10 l, sufficiently little to fit into a traveller's bag. Using the absorber at the floor, advantageously in the middle of a larger room, will allow to take early reflections into account only from walls or the ceiling. Taking the speed of sound propagation, 5 m distance to either wall should allow for almost clean impulse responses for up to 30 ms.

The absorber can also be useful when recording sound samples during performance, for instance when playing in front of a wall. Sound engineers might wish to apply such a simple absorber to get rid of disturbing reflections, for instance when applying close-ups.

References

- [1] DIN EN ISO 354:2003-12, Akustik - Messung der Schallabsorption in Hallräumen (ISO 354:2003); Deutsche Fassung EN ISO 354:2003, Beuth Verlag.
- [2] Sauro, R., Vargas, M., & Mange, G. (2009). Absorption coefficients-part 2: is "edge effect" more important than expected?. *Internoise, Ottawa, Canada, August 2009*.